

A STUDY ON THE FATIGUE CHARACTERISTICS OF SINGLE LAP JOINT BETWEEN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTIC/CARBON STEEL

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Introduction

- In order to meet the requirements of the fuel efficiency regulations, various studies on the weight reduction of vehicles are being conducted
- Especially, many researchers tried to achieve the vehicle weight reduction by applying lightweight materials, e.g. Aluminum, Magnesium, plastics, etc.
- To introduce Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), lightweight and have high mechanical properties-to-weight ratio, into vehicle parts together with traditional materials like carbon steel, structural adhesives are often used to bond them
- In order to ensure the reliability of such components with different materials, long-term properties such as material degradation and fatigue life as well as short-term properties like adhesive strength, should be considered
- In this study...
 - ✓ Carbon steel specimens were treated using sand blasting with different sizes of abrasives and their surface roughness was measured
 - ✓ Fatigue tests were done on lap shear specimens and the relationship between fatigue life and surface roughness was determined

Materials and Test Methods

- Tested adhesive : L-F501 (L&L Products, Epoxy based matrix with a glass veil)
- Substrates
 - Metal : S45C steel plate (thickness of 2 mm)
 - FRP : Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (SKYFLEX USN150AK prepreg, SK Chemicals)
- Surface preparation : Sand blasting on steel surfaces (abrasive : Al₂O₃)
Direct pressure method, air pressure of 5 bar
- Single lap shear specimens were produced by hot pressing (10 MPa, 150°C for 30 min) for fatigue life evaluation, in accordance with ASTM D5868 standard (figure 1)
- Fatigue tests were conducted using MTS 810 universal testing machine

Fig 1. Schematics of fabrication process of steel-CFRP single-lap shear specimens

Results and Discussion

- The application of sand blasting is essential, as the oxide film on the steel surface reduces the shear strength by half (figure 2)
- Smaller particle diameter leads to lower surface roughness (table 1)
- Fatigue tests were conducted (stress ratio of R=0.1, frequency of 10 Hz) on specimens with different surface roughness
- Specimens with smaller surface roughness show longer fatigue life, which is the same trend as shear strength test results (table 1 & figure 3)
- Also, smaller r-square value at high surface roughness suggests that the scattering of data is increased due to irregularities in the surface (remaining oxide film after treatment) (figure 4)

Table 1. The surface roughness and fatigue characteristics according to the grit size of the abrasive

Sand blasting	Grit size	#14	#60	#180
	Particle diameter (μm)	1190	250	88
	Surface roughness, R _a (μm)	4.156	1.786	0.560
Fatigue characteristics	Slope of linear fit, a	-4.568	-4.758	-4.912
	Y-Intercept of linear fit, b	32.60	34.19	35.15
	R-Square	0.9476	0.9543	0.9613

Fig 2. Fracture surface observation after shear strength tests; (a) before removing oxide film and (b) after sand blasted

Fig 4. Remaining oxide film after sand blasted using grit size of #14 (removed from steel surface and attached to the counterpart (CFRP))

Fig 3. S-N fatigue data and curve fits for three different abrasive grit sizes; (a) #14, (b) #60 and (c) #180

Conclusion

- The effect of surface roughness on the fatigue life of carbon steel-CFRP joints is studied
- Abrasives with three different particle sizes were used to obtain different levels of surface roughness
- The smaller the particle size, the lower the surface roughness and the lower surface roughness increases the fatigue life under the same stress level
- Abrasives with large particle sizes can reduce fatigue life by leaving unremoved oxide films on steel surface